

The above procedure has been used over long periods with safety. Moreover, the morphine disappears from the circulation within one hour. This series showed no increase in post-operative chest complications. The technique has been used in major thoracic surgery with success.

It was particularly noticed that the patients in this series were quiet, restful and warm. No case gave any cause for anxiety. No case vomited at operation, two felt nauseated, one of them vomiting five hours after completion of operation; incidence was expressed as 4 per cent.

SUMMARY.

(1) Vomiting and nausea is commoner than is supposed under spinal anaesthesia especially with traction on the meso-appendix.

(2) The use of continuous oxygen and carbon dioxide will prevent these effects in some cases.

(3) Medication with intravenous morphine will prevent these effects in the great majority of cases.

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THE THERAPEUTIC USE OF VITAMIN C.

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SUMMARY.

OBSERVATIONS made upon two sections of R.A.M.C. men dosed with vitamin C gave differences far beyond those that could be attributed to chance. It was ascertained that men of one section were dosed before breakfast, those of the other after it. The latter became saturated and excreted excess vitamin sooner than the former.

In the winter 1941-42 and late spring 1942 an investigation planned by the Hygiene Directorate of the R.A.M.C. to ascertain the vitamin C reserves of troops was carried out by one of us. The method used was that of Harris and Abbasy in which men are dosed with vitamin tablets till an analysis of the urine indicates an approach to saturation; this may take from a few days up to ten or twelve in scorbutic cases. At each station a hundred men were tested; in one instance half were infantry and half R.A.M.C. personnel of a military hospital. The latter were in equal sections, A and B, and it happened to be convenient to dose section A, the infantry and section B in that order starting at 07.30 hrs. Section B went on with their hospital work till required for dosing, at about 08.00 hrs. There were most unexpected differences between the two R.A.M.C. sections. The men shared the same Me.s and had miscellaneous hospital work. They were sections only for A.R.P. and similar duties. Accordingly very different behaviour in these sections appeared to be a severe blow to one's confidence in the method. The results were as follows. Four doses were given; men near saturation after four doses were listed as saturated after five. Five (a) in the table denotes men showing such an increase in excretion as to appear likely to be

saturated after six doses ; five (b) shows those so low after four doses that no prediction could be made.

Urines were collected in the order of dosing, so that the times of retention were as nearly as possible equal.

<i>Doses to saturate</i>	<i>Men A</i>	<i>Men B</i>	<i>Doses</i>	<i>Men A</i>	<i>Men B</i>
1	0	0	5	9	1
2	0	1	5a	1	0
3	4	14	5b	2	0
4	6	5			

Inquiries failed to reveal any difference between the sections, such as age, weight or occupation, to which their behaviour in the test could be attributed. The results were reported without any explanation being possible.

The same hospital was visited four months later and further inquiries elicited the fact that the section A men of the R.A.M.C. had paraded at 07:30 hrs., before breakfast, having been busy attending to patients. Section B men, finding they were not required immediately, had their food and received the dose of vitamin C afterwards. This routine was followed on subsequent days. It appears therefore that vitamin C is much better utilized after other food which is in keeping with the custom of having dessert after meals.

As, however, it was felt that it would be unwise to draw a conclusion from a single experiment, although fifty men were in it, the tabulated results were submitted to statistical analysis to ascertain the probability of the distribution found being due to chance. Of the 43 cases in the two groups to be compared, if one draws a line between the 19 first saturated and the 24 others (that is, between those saturated in the first three days and those taking longer), one has in the first group 4A and 15B, in the second group 18A and 6B. The chance of getting so large a discrepancy, if the numbers in A and B were really proportional, is about 1 : 1,867, so there is no doubt at all of the statistical significance of the difference observed. It can be taken as certainly not due to chance. The only ascertainable difference between the two groups was that men of section A which took longer to saturate had their vitamin C on an empty stomach.

We are indebted to Dr. L. J. Harris for the information that, at a recent Conference on "Wound Healing" organized by the Society for Experimental Biology in Cambridge, it was shown that, if one measures wound healing adequately and quantitatively by a determination of tensile strength, there is an excellent correlation between the level of intake of vitamin C and the tensile strength of the wound. It follows that it is important to know the best conditions for administration of the vitamin in therapeutic doses and that men who go into action with good reserves of vitamin C may come out of hospital somewhat sooner than those who, adequately supplied for normal needs, have no considerable reserve.